

DIS4SME

WP 2 “Knowledge base, methodology and tools”

Deliverable No. 2.2: Demand for skills in ICT SMEs

Carlos Clemente

Imanol Eslava

Javier Arrondo

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Authors	Carlos Clemente, Imanol Eslava, Javier Arrondo
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List of Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
BIM	Building Information Modeling
CAD	Computer Aided Design
CEO	Chief Executive Officer
CIO	Chief Information Officer
CTO	Chief Technology Officer
ETL	Extraction, Transformation, and Loading
ESCO	European Skills, Competences, Qualifications and Occupations
FME	Feature Manipulation Engine
GDAL	Geospatial Data Abstraction Library
GDU	Geographic Data Unit
GIS	Geographic Information System
GML	Geography Markup Language
HALE	HUMBOLDT Alignment Editor
IACS	Integrated Administration and Control System
IFC	Industry Foundation Classes
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IoT	Internet of Things
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation

MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OGR	OpenGIS Simple Features Reference Implementation
RESTful	Representational State Transfer
RDI	Research, Development and Innovation
RID	Research and Development
SLD	Styled Layer Descriptor
SMEs	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
WCS	Web Coverage Service
WFS	Web Feature Service
WMS	Web Map Service

Executive Summary

The deliverable 2.2, titled "Demand for skills in ICT SMEs" aims to analyse the skills shortages, gaps, and mismatches between the supply of vocational and academic training in the field of location data interoperability and the current demand for skills in the market. It also aims to define which professional profiles are the most relevant in terms of employment opportunities linked to location data interoperability.

To accomplish these objectives, an in-depth exploration was conducted through an online survey and a series of interviews, which aimed to uncover the knowledge, needs, and challenges experienced by interviewees in various companies and countries concerning location data interoperability. The ultimate goal was to identify gaps and discrepancies between the skills provided by vocational and academic training and those demanded when dealing with location data interoperability.

The insights gained from this task will serve as the cornerstone for identifying a set of business case studies supporting the design of a training curriculum to be developed in subsequent stages of WP2 and WP3. The evaluation encompassed more than one hundred surveys and over twenty interviews with experts from both within and outside the European Union. Furthermore, the information gained from the deliverable 2.1, which outlines the current training landscape, played a crucial role in shaping the results outlined above.

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of the document

The deliverable D2.2 is the result of Task 2.2, having these three main objectives:

1. Analyse the skills shortages, gaps, and mismatches between the supply of vocational and academic training in the field of location data interoperability (T2.1) and the current market demand for skills. Define which occupational profiles are most promising in terms of job opportunities.
2. Prepare and conduct a survey and a series of interviews in order to assess what knowledge gaps, issues and difficulties in location data interoperability companies face across EU and extra EU countries.
3. Identify skills shortages, gaps, and mismatches between demand and offer of training in the field of location data interoperability.

The document analyses in the following chapters all the pieces of information provided by the different professionals who have participated in the activities of this work package, and conclusions are drawn to ease the decision-making process.

Furthermore, it delineates the most relevant occupational profiles concerning location data interoperability. This analysis extends to proposing strategies for enhancing relevant skills, which can play a pivotal role in fostering growth across various industry sectors.

1.2. Relation to other activities

Task 2.2 is tightly connected with other tasks of WP2, namely:

Task 2.1: This task identifies topics and accessible/reusable training materials to be used as input for the business case studies to be developed. It also identifies trends, challenges and opportunities in the field and their possible impact on the existing occupational market. The combination of the data obtained in T2.1 with T2.2 has allowed to identify and analyse gaps between the current training offer and the needs of the companies participating in the online survey and interviews.

Task 2.3: This task specifies the most suitable training methods, processes and tools required for co-creation of knowledge in the context of DIS4SME. The task will also use the outputs from the T2.1 and T2.2 for the purpose of an initial definition of the business case studies to be developed.

Task 2.4: This task designs the DIS4SME Curriculum. A list of training requirements and needs are identified based on the gaps and mismatches from task 2.2, which leads to the definition of a detailed outline of training actions, including the final list of training courses to be developed.

1.3. Structure of the document

This deliverable comprises four chapters in addition to chapter 1, which serves as the introduction.

Chapter 2 provides a comprehensive analysis of the data collection process. Section 2.1 presents a concise overview of survey responses, along with a detailed analysis and conclusions. In Section 2.2, summaries of the interviews categorized by country are provided.

Chapter 3 offers a summary of the professional profiles related to location data interoperability.

Chapter 4 offers an analysis of the gap between the current educational offer and the business needs in the field of location data interoperability.

Lastly, Chapter 5 presents the concluding remarks.

In the document's appendix, annexes that include the online survey and interview model and data visualization graphs for each survey question are provided.

2. Methods of data collection

The primary objective of Task 2.2 is to gather a comprehensive range of insights from various professionals regarding their activities and challenges in the context of location data interoperability. This effort is aimed at extracting current training needs and identifying gaps within the existing educational offer and the expertise landscape.

To achieve this information, two methods were used:

- Interviews of selected experts in location data interoperability in different industry sectors.
- An online survey designed to engage a broad user base, with a specific emphasis on the geospatial community.

All project partners actively participated in the data collection process. Each partner was tasked with not only distributing the online survey within their respective contacts and networks but also with identifying and reaching out to well-suited candidates for the interviews.

Interviews of experts

To facilitate the interviews, a comprehensive set of documentation was prepared:

- A guide with the basic interview questions. The list of questions was indicative, and the interviewer was free to give more weight to certain aspects depending on the context and profile of the interviewee). The guide also contained an organisational schema to perform the interviews including information of the time needed and other technical/operational aspects to perform the interview in the most professional way possible. This guide was sent to all project partners.
- A model for the letter of invitation for the interviewees to be sent by mail.
- A template to collect and structure the interview responses in a homogeneous way for all partners.
- A document containing the proposals of professionals to be interviewed by the partners.
- A table for monitoring and ensuring a transparent tracking of contributions from each partner.

Several basic questions for the interview were prepared with the aim of uncovering challenges and skill-related requirements. These questions are available in the annex of this document.

It was agreed by all the partners that the interview format could be conducted either through a structured document sent via email, conducted online, or in person, offering partners the flexibility to choose the method that best suited their individual needs. The sole requirement was to provide the task leader with interview outcomes using a standardized template, ensuring ease of analysis for the collected responses. Also, all these interviews were conducted in compliance with EU data protection standards.

For the online interviews the interviewees were asked to give their express authorisation to be recorded so that the transcript could be used to obtain more easily the relevant information from the interview, others showed great interest in the project and provided their email address to receive information about the results. In all instances, it was assured to the interviewees that any personal information or data enabling their identification would not be published in any manner.

The estimated duration of the online and face-to-face interview was between 15 and 30 minutes, but the interview durations often exceeded the 30-minute mark. The interviewees initially came from the countries of the project partners (Italy, Belgium, Slovenia, Croatia and Spain) but thanks to the wide European network of contacts of the partners, companies in other countries were reached as well.

The interviews were conducted in the interviewee's preferred language to enhance accessibility and communication and each interview was reported in a common template.

On-line survey

The partners involved in Task 2.2 designed an online survey that was disseminated not only in member countries, but also Europe-wide. The main objective of the survey was to identify common challenges and training needs in the field of location data interoperability to be addressed in European SMEs. The specific objectives of the survey were the following:

- Identify the skills needed to deal with location data interoperability projects for different job positions and in relation to nationality and business sector.
- Recognize the most typical interoperability problems when working with location data and how to solve them.
- To assess the level of knowledge and skills possessed by individuals involved in location data interoperability tasks.
- To better understand which topics and learning materials would be of interest, with the aim of addressing knowledge and skill gaps in the field of location data interoperability.

The on-line survey has also allowed us to approach companies and organizations offering them information about the DIS4SME project and asking them to subscribe to the project's newsletter.

It was agreed to design the online survey using the EUSurvey platform. EUSurvey is the official survey management tool of the European Commission and is used to create and publish survey forms. The application, hosted by the European Commission's Digital Services Department (DG DIGIT), is available free of charge to all EU citizens.

In terms of survey distribution and promotion, all project partners have actively engaged by leveraging their distribution channels, social media platforms, newsletters, and more. Additionally, the dedicated dissemination work package of the project (WP5) has played a pivotal role in promoting the survey across the project's social channels (Twitter¹, Facebook² and LinkedIn³), website news⁴ and media⁵, such as the leaflets and the first issue of the project newsletter.

The online survey was officially launched on June 20, 2023, and was open until 31 August. The online survey is featured in the project website at this link⁶.

The EOSurvey form can be accessed directly at this link⁷.

Desktop research

The third method that was proposed for data collection was the desktop research. "Desktop research" refers to the process of gathering information, data, and insights from existing sources, typically through online databases, publications, reports, and other readily available materials.

For this, a template was created for the partners to upload their research on the information they could find, but this method offered limited results compared to the interviews and online survey.

The documentary information significantly overlapped with the findings from task T2.1. This prompted us to reconsider the value of continuing with documentary research. Consequently, the task focused on the analysis of the feedback received through the interviews and the online survey.

¹ <https://twitter.com/dis4sme>

² <https://www.facebook.com/dis4sme/>

³ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/dis4sme-project>

⁴ <https://www.dis4sme.eu/2023/06/20/dis4sme-survey-launched/>

⁵ <https://www.dis4sme.eu/media/>

⁶ <https://www.dis4sme.eu/survey/>

⁷ <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/DIS4SME>

2.1. Online survey analysis

The DIS4SME online survey was designed with the main objective of identifying concrete demands for knowledge, skills and competences coming from the respondents that are relevant in the field of location data interoperability. In addition to the interview responses, the idea was to create a questionnaire composed mainly of closed multiple choice questions to collect answers within a limited framework of options. With closed questions we can obtain clean and easy to analyse data.

The survey has been designed to be completed in approximately 10-15 minutes. The full list of survey questions, along with a link to the graphical results, is available in Annex 1 of this report.

The survey is structured in 2 sections:

- Section 1: You and your organisation.
- Section 2: Knowledge and needs in location data interoperability.

Section 1 aims to collect information on the background and professional profile of the respondents. This section also asks for information on the type of company/organisation in which the respondents work,

Section 2 mainly aims to identify interoperability issues when dealing with location data and how to resolve them. In this section, respondents are also asked to specify and assess the level of knowledge required for a range of technical skills and competencies.

In the final part of the survey, participants have the possibility to provide their personal data in order to be informed of the results of the survey and of the project in general. The management of this information is done in compliance with the Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation). In this regard, twenty-one respondents opted to provide their personal information, while the remaining respondents chose to remain anonymous.

The EU Survey tool permits to filter the results based on selected criteria. This feature is extremely useful when analysing the results of the surveys in relation to aspects such as the origin of the respondents or their professional profile.

The analysis of the main findings from survey responses grouped for each of the survey sections is given in the next subsection. Also, the complete survey results and figures are available as the Annex 1 of this report.

2.1.2. Survey results

The analysis of the survey results is considering the 105 questionnaires filled in as of 31 August 2023. The survey is still open, and questionnaires received after the closure date will be analysed subsequently and considered but will not be part of this report.

The survey responses offer a representative overview of the situation in each partner country as well as in other European countries. This comprehensive data allows us to gain a good understanding of the training requirements for location data interoperability across various fields and sectors.

Below is provided an analysis of the main findings from the online survey responses grouped for each of the survey sections. The complete survey results and figures are available in the Annex 1 of this report.

Survey section 1: “You and your organisation”

When examining the organizational affiliations of our respondents, the survey reveals that almost 48% of them are connected to small and medium enterprises (SMEs).

It's worth highlighting the significant number of responses received from employees of public organizations (more than 20%). Additional responses originate from training providers, comprising over 6%, and non-profit organizations, accounting for nearly 12%.

Regarding the number of answers by country, we can say that the distribution is quite balanced, among partner countries, although it is worth noting the high interest from respondents in Italy and Spain. This can be easily attributed to the project's collaboration with two business associations, namely AIN, in Spain and SIIT, in Italy.

- Italy: twenty-eight respondents
- Spain: twenty-seven respondents
- Croatia: thirteen respondents
- Germany: seven respondents
- Slovenia: ten respondents
- Belgium: five respondents
- France: two respondents
- European organisation: two respondents

- Other countries: eight respondents (Bulgaria, Hungary, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Sweden)
- Other non-EU country: three respondents (Georgia, Switzerland and Turkey)

Regarding the business sector in which the respondents work, the results are also well balanced. Most of the respondents work in the Software development/distribution sector (almost 52% of the respondents). It is noteworthy that almost the 25% of the respondents work in the training and education sector. Other relevant sectors are: Environment (21%), Industry (20%), Agriculture (18%), Transportation and logistics (18%), Energy (18%), Architecture, engineering and construction (16%), Mobility (11%) and Urban Planning (12%).

Finally, less represented sectors are Utilities (10% of the respondents), Health (7%), Tourism and hospitality (7%), Real estate (4%), and Cultural heritage (4%). It should be considered that this question is a multiple-choice question. Therefore, many respondents choose more than one sector to describe their profile.

Integrating location data from diverse sources and formats is basically a technical challenge. The prevalence of people working in the software development/distribution sector can be attributed to the fact that location data interoperability often requires the development and integration of software solutions to ensure that data from different sources can be effectively used together. Also, software development allows for the customization of solutions to meet specific needs. In summary, the software development/distribution sector plays a crucial role in addressing the complex challenges associated with location data interoperability, making it a natural fit for professionals in this field.

Finally, regarding the role in the organization, most of the respondents are project managers (29%), followed by owners or chief executive officers (22%). Furthermore, roles within the education and training sector are prominently featured, encompassing trainers, professors, and researchers, constituting 20% of the respondents.

Survey section 2: “Your knowledge and needs in location data interoperability”.

In this section, the two first questions are related to the familiarity of the respondents with the concept of location data interoperability and the level of expertise and experience working with it.

In general, the respondents are somewhat (46%) or very (40%) familiar with the concept. In fact, the concept of location data interoperability is not as well-known as other types of interoperability, such as data exchange standards or system integration. However, it is becoming increasingly important as more and more devices and applications collect and use location data. As the use of location data

continues to grow, location data interoperability will become increasingly important. Only 12% of the respondents indicated that they are not familiar at all with this concept.

Regarding the level of expertise in relation to using and integrating location data, 36% of the respondents claim to have an intermediate level of expertise. It is highlighted that there are more respondents with an expert level (32%) than with a basic level (26%). Therefore, it is likely that the survey has been primarily completed by individuals who are familiar with and have work experience in the field of data interoperability.

Analysing the level of expertise by country, it is noteworthy that almost the 70% of Croatian respondents have an expert level while in the rest of countries most respondents have an intermediate level of competence. Considering the profile of the respondents, owners/chief executive officers and chief technology/chief information officer are in general slightly more familiar with the concept than project managers. The same tendency can be observed with the level of expertise using and integrating location data.

Regarding the respondents with an educational or training profile, very few of them have an expert level (13%) in relation to using and integrating location data. Location data interoperability is a relatively new field and the concept is still evolving. As a result, there is not a lot of educational material available on the topic and is not a core competency for most educators. In addition, most educators may not have the knowledge or skills necessary to teach it to their students.

Question 2.3 of the survey (“Have you ever experienced issues in one or more of the following location interoperability aspects?”) is maybe the most important question of the survey. The question aims at identifying relevant problems and challenges encountered while working with location data interoperability. These responses serve as the foundation for identifying the knowledge, skills, and competences that need to be acquired to effectively address these issues.

In general, respondents experienced in a greater or lesser degree all the interoperability issues considered in the provided list and, while of course some issues are more common than others, it appears that no single type of problem is significantly more relevant than the others.

The most frequently mentioned problems are related to data format compatibility integrating geospatial data with other geospatial or non-geospatial data stored in various formats (70%).

Also very relevant are problems when using and exchanging location data across different tools, platforms, or software systems (almost 64%). Other important issues are data access and sharing problems due to legal or licensing restrictions and lack of sharing standards (56%) and converting

geospatial data provided with different coordinate systems (55%). Also, almost half of the respondents have problems with semantics schema mapping and data harmonization/transformation, that is an extremely important aspect in the context of location data interoperability.

Other issues that occur in fewer cases are problems when sharing, exchanging, and using location data generated and managed by multiple organisations (40%) and legal interoperability problems regarding security, data protection, intellectual property rights (29%).

Comparing the situation per country, in all of them the main two problems are aspects related to data format compatibility and interoperability between tools and platforms.

Another key question in this section was aimed at identifying the more popular types of data needed for integration with other location or non-location data. The purpose of this question was to identify industry sectors where the requirement for location data integration is more significant. Users were able to choose as many options as they wanted, and the result gave the following ranking:

1. Image and raster data (satellite imagery, aerial photographs, or scanned maps) (61%).
2. Temperature, humidity, air quality, or any other meteorological or environmental parameters. (48%)
3. Business data (customer information, sales data, or stock market data) (34%)
4. Demographic information or population statistics (32%)

Other types of data that our respondents found less relevant were economic indicators (23%), healthcare statistics (19%), cultural heritage (15%), and social media data (social media feeds, check-ins, and user-generated content) (9%).

This result provides valuable insights into the priority areas where location data integration plays an important role within various industries. Overall, these statistics highlight the diverse and widespread applications of location data integration across various industries. The varying percentages reflect the specific needs and priorities, with image and raster data, meteorological information, and business data being particularly prominent.

Image and Raster Data, with the highest percentage of 61%, indicates a strong demand for integrating visual data sources like satellite imagery. This suggests that industries relying on geospatial visualization, such as agriculture, urban planning, and environmental monitoring, greatly benefit from integration of location data. Also, the significant interest in meteorological and environmental data integration (e.g., temperature, humidity, air quality) at 48% highlights the

importance of weather-related information for various sectors, including agriculture, energy, transportation, and disaster management.

A key question of the DIS4SME survey deals with the identification and assessment of concrete competencies and skills required to cope with location data interoperability. To assess respondents' knowledge of tools and standards for sharing and integrating location data, we asked them to rate their expertise level as "basic," "intermediate," "expert," or "no knowledge" for several well-known and relevant tools and standards. In fact, standards play a critical role in location data interoperability. They provide a common language for describing, storing, and exchanging location data.

The following analysis will mainly consider the overall final result of this question but, when relevant, some differences on the weight given to each knowledge, skill and competency depending on the professional field and sector of the respondents, is also provided.

Overall, the respondents had significant knowledge and expertise in tools and standards for sharing and integrating data using web services standards, geospatial data standards, and GIS software tools.

In detail, concerning the use of web services standards of sharing and integrating data (such as the Web Map Service (WMS), Web Feature Service (WFS), and Web Coverage Service (WCS)), more than the 60% of the respondents has an intermediate or expert level; and only a 17% recognized not having any knowledge. The similar percentage is observed in the assessment of knowledge on Geospatial Data Standards (such as Geography Markup Language (GML), Keyhole Markup Language (KML), GeoJSON and GeoPackage).

GIS software tools (such as ArcGIS, QGIS, and other tools) are those in which respondents have the most experience and expertise. More than the 40% of the respondents has an expert level.

When asking for the assessment of using Spatial Metadata Standards, the percentage of respondents with an expert level dramatically decrease; and more than a half express not having any knowledge or a basic one. Regarding the Spatial Processing and Analysis Standards such as Web Processing Service (WPS) or Styled Layer Descriptor (SLD) also most of the respondents admit having a basic level.

The most unknown tools and standards are Sensor Data Standards, with 40% of the respondents with no knowledge; 3D and city model standards, with 37% of the respondents with no knowledge; and Semantic Web Standards, with 42% of the respondents with no knowledge. In fact, Semantic Web Services standards has the highest percentage of respondents without knowledge.

Lastly, Integration Conversion and Transformation tools (Such as FME⁸, ogr2ogr, GDAL and HALE⁹) are not as well-known than GIS software tools in relation to data interoperability, as the 34% of the respondents has no knowledge using them and only 14% has an expert level. Poor knowledge regarding these crucial tools is likely because GIS software is more widely used and marketed, and that these ICT tools can be more complex to use. Our survey suggests that there is a significant gap in knowledge and skills in this area and that there is a need to raise awareness and to provide training and support for those who want to learn how to use these tools.

A ranking of the best known or more used tools and standards in an intermediate or expert level for sharing and integrating location data could be made with these results:

1. GIS software tools, with more than 70% of the respondents with intermediate or expert level (43%).
2. Web Services Standards, with more than 60% of the respondents with intermediate or expert level.
3. Spatial Metadata Standards, with 44% of the respondents with intermediate or expert level.
4. Integration Conversion and Transformation tools, with 44% of the respondents with intermediate or expert level.
5. Spatial Processing and Analysis Standards, with only 28% of the respondents with an intermediate or expert level.
6. Sensor Data Standards, with only 28% of the respondents with an intermediate or expert level.
7. 3D and city model standards, with only 25% of the respondents with an intermediate or expert level.
8. Semantic Web Services standards, with only 25% of the respondents with an intermediate or expert level.

The final question in this section was focused on uncovering the types of training resources that our respondents find most appealing for enhancing their knowledge in location data interoperability.

⁸ <https://fme.safe.com/>

⁹ <https://wetransform.to/halestudio/>

The result of the question shows that distance learning (e-learning) short courses is considered to be the most interesting type of training (71%), followed by short online videos (58%), online workshops (56%), and webinars (54%). This leads to think that in general there is a preference for short duration courses and online or e-learning courses over technical guides, slides or presentations. In addition, a high percentage of respondents (48%) found the hands-on tutorials interesting.

In the survey's concluding part, respondents were invited to share additional comments. They were also provided with the option to receive updates regarding the survey's follow-up and information about DIS4SME.

In terms of respondents' interest in DIS4SME results, 39 individuals from various sectors have expressed a desire to stay informed about the project.

2.1.3. Survey conclusions

The analysis of the survey results, which included 105 questionnaires filled out by August 31, 2023, offers valuable insights into the training requirements for location data interoperability across various fields and sectors.

Regarding the respondent characteristics, approximately 48% are affiliated with small and medium enterprises (SMEs), while roughly 52% work within the software development/distribution sector. Additionally, about 25% of respondents are employed in the education and training sector. The respondent roles are varied, with project managers constituting 29%, followed closely by owners/chief executive officers at 22%.

Regarding primary challenges in location data interoperability, respondents encounter a range of challenges, and no single issue stands out as significantly more relevant than others. Noteworthy challenges include data format compatibility (70%), interoperability between tools/platforms (64%), data access/sharing legal issues (56%), and converting geospatial data with different coordinate systems (55%).

Concerning types of data, prominent data integration needs include image and raster data (61%) and meteorological/environmental parameters (48%).

Regarding expertise in tools and standards, respondents demonstrate proficiency in using web services standards (60% with intermediate/expert level) and GIS software tools (75% with intermediate/expert level). However, there is a lack of expertise in using conversion and transformation tools that definitely will be taken into account when defining our training curricula.

As for training resources preferences, the preferred training format among respondents is distance learning (e-learning) short courses (71%). Other popular training formats include short online videos (58%) and online workshops (56%).

Overall, the survey results suggest that there is a need for more awareness and understanding of location data interoperability, as well as training and support on how to use the necessary tools and technologies. In addition, the survey results suggest that there is a market opportunity for training providers to develop and deliver courses on location data interoperability.

From the received responses, we can learn about training requirements for location data interoperability across various fields and sectors and this information is crucial in view of the definition of the DIS4SME training offer. The most frequently mentioned problems related to location data interoperability are data format compatibility and problems when using and exchanging location data across different tools, platforms, or software systems. The analysis also identifies the more popular types of data needed for integration with other location or non-location data and stresses the need of teaching on how to use conversion and transformation tools, as well as how to integrate specific types of data.

2.2. Interviews analysis

To collect information of skills demand on location data interoperability and assess current trends and need of digital SMEs, DIS4SME under the task 2.2 carried out also interviews to selected experts and SME owners.

In this section the answers collected through the interviews are presented, with reference to the country where the interviewed subjects live and work.

Totally 24 interviews were conducted, with the following geographical distribution:

- Italy: 10

- Spain: 5
- Croatia: 4
- Belgium: 4
- Sweden: 1

The interviews aimed to gather first-hand information from a diverse group of individuals, including owners and workers of digital SMEs, ICT and thematic experts, and professionals from various industrial sectors. With a strong emphasis on participation from DIS4SME countries, the interviews provided valuable insights into the digital landscape and its impact on businesses.

By comparing responses from different countries, it was possible to identify areas where there is broad consensus or disagreement on a particular argument. This information can be used to tailor educational initiatives and develop educational resources in each of the participating countries depending on specific knowledge gaps.

The comprehensive summaries of each conducted interview can be found in the annex¹⁰ of this document.

2.2.2.1. Interviews in ITALY

The interviews from Italy differ both in type of organization and professional profiles who participated in the initiative. Most interviewed subjects were from ICT SMEs, but interviews came also from professionals of public sector and large companies, giving a larger overview of current gaps and needs for skills.

Interviewed profiles.

Most of the interviewed subjects had a high-level education in science and computer science. Their professional profiles can be categorized as follows:

- Public officer - data management service
- Academics / Professors.
- CEOs and founder.
- CTOs

¹⁰ The Annex includes reports on 22 out of the total number of 24 interviews that were conducted.

- Information System and Project Manager.
- Project Manager and Technical Manager.

Fields of activity

The interviewed subjects were from organizations in a variety of sectors, including geolocation, mobility data and traffic simulations, decision support systems, cloud computing, services in Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and environmental monitoring.

These organizations use location data to provide real-time geolocation and positioning services, develop traffic simulations, develop decision support systems, provide software and management solutions, and provide high-technology GIS solutions,

Tools

Some relevant tools for data interoperability used for the development of all the above activities/products are the following:

- **Kibana and Tableau** are both data visualization tools, Overall, Tableau is more flexible than Kibana in terms of data interoperability. Tableau can be used to visualize data from a wider range of sources, and it has built-in connectors for many popular data sources. However, Kibana is more tightly integrated with Elasticsearch, and it can be used to visualize large amounts of data more efficiently.
- **GeoPandas** is an open-source Python library that extends the pandas library to provide support for geospatial data. GeoPandas is a powerful tool for data interoperability. It allows users to work with geospatial data from a variety of sources in a consistent and unified way. This makes it possible to combine data from different sources to create new insights and visualizations.
- **GeoServer** is a powerful tool for data interoperability in the geospatial domain. It allows users to share and publish geospatial data in a consistent and unified way.

Location data interoperability issues and challenges

The interviews highlighted various problems and challenges associated with location data interoperability, including:

- The need for standardized tools: Respondents emphasized the necessity of having standards for different tools to ensure seamless interoperability.
- Data diversity and collaboration hurdles: Dealing with different types of data and coordinating their joint development posed significant barriers. Additionally, privacy policies governing data sharing between companies and countries were identified as a challenge.
- Academic-practical misalignment: A notable issue emerged regarding the misalignment between academia, which holds advanced theoretical knowledge, and the private/public sector, responsible for practical application.
- Lack of awareness: One interviewee expressed concerns about a general lack of awareness regarding rules and regulations related to location data interoperability.
- Knowledge gaps: Respondents pointed out a lack of basic knowledge and understanding of GIS (Geographic Information Systems), tool usage, and working with satellite data as a significant challenge.

Most of the interviewees provided comments and recommendations on data interoperability aspects, the most relevant are the following:

- The technical and semantic layers of interoperability can be seen as priorities, but legal interoperability is also important.
- Training should follow European priorities, in particular those related to the European Green Deal (environmental sector).
- To overcome this mismatch and guarantee interoperability, focus training on knowing standards is essential.
- It is important that all public administrations use the same geographical spatial references to avoid inconsistencies.
- New AI systems could encourage new models of location data interoperability or improve the performance of existing ones.

- Interoperability is important in all sectors. One criterion for prioritisation could be the areas where human health is involved: Health, Emergencies and Security.
- Geospatial data integration is vital across sectors like epidemiology and geomarketing.
- Priority sectors for interoperability are renewable energy, environmental monitoring, and territorial planning.
- The area of dynamic sensor data is a priority in terms of location data interoperability.

Needs for training.

All the interviewed subjects recognised the need for specific training and courses in the field of location data interoperability, to boost their activity and business. They expressed two different points of view:

- Need for courses on general topics / knowledge base in the field of location data interoperability and related data policies, to open them the possibility of spanning in different field of activities.
- Need to enhance technical problem-solving skills, it's crucial to take advanced and specialized courses that provide insights into the appropriate tools and standards to be used. These courses can help individuals develop the necessary expertise to tackle complex technical challenges. Effective training should be remote, lasting around 18-20 hours, and software focused.

These interview findings highlight the need to tailor different types of courses to the job profiles involved in location data interoperability. Training should be modular and cover different levels of knowledge, from the most basic to the most technical and practical.

2.2.2.2. Interviews in SPAIN

The companies engaged in the interviews are predominantly composed of large enterprises, with the sole exception of one SME. All these companies work in the fields of geolocation, hydrometeorology and risk management, early warning and decision support, cartography, digital transformation, fiscal management, territory management, citizen services; also, in growing sectors such as digitization of agriculture, livestock, smart irrigation models, agri-food.

The professional profiles of the interviewees in Spain are the following:

- CIO (Chief Information Officer)
- Operation director & Head of the software engineering department
- Commercial & business development manager
- RDI Manager

The main problems that interviewees have in their work are the interconnection of data between companies, the standardisation of the data format, or the privacy of data.

When these companies seek to expand their work to other areas or collaborate with other companies, they find that the data collected is not usable across platforms and systems or they see many limitations when sharing work developed in different software.

One of the companies tries to solve these problems using APIS (RESTful if possible). In fact, RESTful APIs offer several benefits for data interoperability, making it easier for different systems and applications to interact with each other.

Finally, when asked about receiving courses they said they preferred online education versus face to face, they also expressed their interest in high level courses in location data interoperability as most had reached a "medium level" through being self-taught or receiving courses that were found on the internet.

2.2.2.3. Interviews in CROATIA

All the interviewed companies in Croatia primarily concentrate on data interoperability, emphasizing its localization component and the associated technologies for data management. The interviewed companies are active in the fields of integrated water resource management and software applications for transportation and energy infrastructures.

In general, all companies work with both raster and vector data. They use satellite data, cadastral parcels, GDU (Geographic Data Unit) data, INSPIRE data, remote sensing data and the information provided by the WISE and EIONET networks.

The professional profiles that participated in the interview are:

- CEO
- Special Advisor for Information Systems.
- Director of GIS operations.

- Head of the business sector of public administration.
- GIS Senior Consultant.

All of them are graduates in Geodesy. The profile of the people who work in these organizations are:

- Engineers of geodesy.
- Electrical engineering.
- Mathematics.
- Informatics and others.

The primary data interoperability issues revolve around the absence of standardized procedures, as each piece of data requires individual adjustments. Other noteworthy aspects regarding location data interoperability from the interviews include the following:

- data to be used or managed is semantically inconsistent. Usually, a lot of effort must be invested to make this data useful.
- There are not many applications that aggregate data from different systems.
- The most critical requirements include data harmonization, data ETL (Extract, Transform, Load), and data preprocessing.

The tools described by the interviewees as the ones they work with or are interested in are as follows:

- GeoServer (WMS, WFS)
- GeoWebCache
- GDAL/OGR
- QGIS
- Open Geospatial Consortium standards
- INSPIRE directive data models.

2.2.2.4. Interviews in SWEDEN

An interview was conducted with an experienced GIS professor and consultant. Two key points this interviewee makes regarding his own experience are:

- Semantic problems are the most challenging data iteration aspects. Data harmonisation and schema transformation problems can be solved using HALE software, for instance on the Harmonisation to INSPIRE data models.
- It seems that the data integration business is going in the JSON direction. Many data integration service companies are providing solutions based on JSON as the main data exchange mechanism.

The fields on which the interviewee focuses his strategies for consultation, development and study of the material are BIM and GIS data and sensor data. The main problems he encounters daily in these fields are as follows:

- BIM data: Flattening IFC data, from IFC/STEP to for instance JSON, is not straightforward with open-source tools.
- Sensor data: Adherence to OGC Sensor Things API standard is limited. Creates problems since QGIS has stopped supporting the OGC SWE standard.

He mentions that the main platform for GIS is QGIS and for schema transformation, HALE. If there are no open-source tools available, the problems are fixed with Python.

Finally, the interviewee mentioned that there are currently no training programs provided by Swedish academic institutions or training providers for professionals in the field of location data interoperability.

2.2.2.5. Interviews in BELGIUM

The profiles interviewed in Belgium were:

- Expert in data exchange systems development.
- Senior project manager of a large company working with aerial surveying, remote sensing, and geographic data.

The main problems described in the interviews are the following:

- Interoperability problems are mainly on coordinate and projection systems for data from different sources, missing metadata, export data to desired formats and very important semantic and terminology issues.

- Challenges in establishing a platform for exchanging IACS data with farmers and partners, particularly in the identification of pre-existing data standards to work with. IACS is a collection of data that is used to manage and control the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) in the European Union.

From the interviews, we can identify several relevant tools and techniques for addressing location data interoperability issues. The most relevant are:

- Use of FME to solve most interoperability problems and data conversions.
- Use of standards such as CityGML for 3D-city models to overcome interoperability problems.

2.2.3. Interview conclusions

The interviews conducted in various countries showcased a diverse range of professional profiles that participated in the discussions about location data interoperability. These profiles included individuals from both public and private sectors, such as public officers, CEOs, project managers, technical experts, and consultants.

It is noteworthy the wide array of educational backgrounds, with many interviewees having strong education in fields like computer science, geodesy, engineering, mathematics, and informatics. This diversity emphasized the cross-disciplinary nature of location data interoperability and the need for collaboration among experts from different domains.

The participants ranged from small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) to larger companies, including companies specialized in fields like geolocation, risk management, digitization of agriculture, hydrometeorology. This diversity highlighted the relevance of location data interoperability across various business sectors.

Across the interviews, several common challenges were highlighted. The issue of data standardization and format consistency was a recurring theme, as it posed hurdles when integrating data from different sources. Privacy concerns also emerged as a challenge, particularly when sharing data between companies and countries. A noteworthy challenge was the misalignment between academia and practical application. Interviewees emphasized the need to bridge this gap and bring theoretical knowledge into practical projects effectively.

The interviews mentioned a diverse array of tools and technologies employed to address location data interoperability challenges. Some relevant are:

- Geographic Information System (GIS) software, such as QGIS, was a common tool used for location data manipulation and analysis.
- Data transformation tools like FME (Feature Manipulation Engine) and HALE (The Humboldt Alignment Editor), play a crucial role in handling data harmonization and schema transformation.
- Emerging technologies like Artificial Intelligence (AI) and the Internet of Things (IoT) were also discussed in the context of advancing interoperability capabilities.
- Each data provider has a different system and format for data provision and sharing. Best way to share data is via RESTful API's but not all providers do this.
- SMEs must convert data from providers to their own standard most of the times. Standards for data sharing are crucial in this sense but underused.

Data harmonization and semantic interoperability needs in general emerged as a central concern across all interviews. With data originating from diverse sources and adhering to various standards, achieving semantic and technical consistency is often a complex challenge. Tools like FME, HALE and Python programming were cited as essential tools to address schema transformations and data harmonization. The emphasis on this challenge highlighted the critical role of accurate and harmonized data in ensuring effective location data interoperability.

Many interviewees expressed interest in exploring advanced topics such as big data, machine learning, application programming interfaces (APIs), and conversion tools. There was a recognition that staying up to date with emerging trends and technologies is essential for driving innovation and remaining competitive in the field.

A common idea expressed in the interviews was the gap between theoretical knowledge, typically found in academic settings, and its practical application in real-world projects. The need for education that focused on hands-on problem-solving and addressed the challenges encountered during actual projects was widely recognized. The consensus among interviewees was the crucial need for training to address the existing gaps in knowledge and skills related to location data interoperability. There was a recognition that the field is evolving rapidly and that keeping up with the latest advancements is essential. The interest in training was not limited to any specific profile or sector; both public and private sectors expressed enthusiasm for new learning opportunities. The preference for training

formats varied, with online courses being favoured for their flexibility, while some preferred face-to-face interactions for focused skill development.

Regarding training formats, there was diversity in preferences. Some interviewees leaned towards internal training within their organizations, while others were more interested in seeking specialized courses from external providers. Many professionals, especially those managing busy schedules, found online courses to be convenient and flexible. However, for more focused skill development, face-to-face interactions were often preferred.

In conclusion, the information gathered from these interviews, unlike the online survey, offers a broader perspective enriched by the knowledge and experience of the interviewees. This provides us with invaluable insights into the current dynamics within companies.

The interviews conducted across various countries and professional backgrounds highlighted the common challenges experienced in the field of location data interoperability. The recurring themes included the demand for more training, tools, and standards to improve interoperability capabilities, as well as the goal of overcoming the separation between theoretical knowledge and practical implementation.

3. Definition of professional profiles for location data interoperability

The following section deals with the professional profiles that can be found in the field of location data interoperability and that we consider should be the ones targeted by the training material to be developed in DIS4SME.

These are defined and selected through the analysis of the information obtained from the results of the interviews and the online survey as well as the knowledge and experience of educational experts. The profiles to be defined will be the following:

- Owner/manager/CEO/CTO of an SME (ESCO code 121115)
- ICT Specialist (ESCO code 252221) / GIS Specialist (ESCO code 252224)

The profiles listed are ESCO profiles. ESCO stands for European Skills, Competences, Occupations and Qualifications. It is a classification system that provides a common language for describing skills, competences, occupations, and qualifications across Europe.

Based on the interviews, it becomes evident that focusing into highly specific profiles may not be practical. This is because the skills identified as essential by the interviewees may be relevant across various professional roles. Further segmentation could complicate the identification of the target audience for the upcoming courses.

Brief descriptions of each profile are as follows:

Owner/Manager/CEO/CTO of an ICT SME

This profile is expected to lead and coordinate projects to develop and implement location data interoperability solutions. They need to be trained in the basics of location data interoperability and in this sense should have the following knowledge, skills and competencies:

- Understanding of the basics of location data interoperability: This includes basic understanding on the benefits of location data interoperability, the different types of location data, the different formats in which location data is stored, and the different standards and tools that can be used to share and integrate location data.

- Ability to identify and assess location data needs: This includes being able to understand the different ways in which location data can be used in a business and being able to identify and assess the specific location data needs of a business.
- Being able to manage the development and implementation of solutions to share and integrate location data and being able to use location data to improve business processes and decision-making.
- Being able to communicate, define and develop business cases, defining skills development programmes, etc, in relation to data interoperability challenges.
- Have knowledge on the main EU policies and public resources related to location data interoperability such as INSPIRE, European Location Framework, Copernicus Programme, PSI Directive, Open Data Strategy for Europe and the European Data Portal.

In addition to the above skills, this profile should also have general skills (that are out of the scope of the training to be developed in DIS4SME) such as leadership and management skills, business and strategic planning skills and communication and interpersonal skills:

ICT Specialist / GIS Specialist

This profile is expected to deal mainly with technical challenges and data management. Therefore, they need to be trained in the basics of location data interoperability and also in advanced, technical and practical training providing the necessary knowledge and skills to implement data integration tasks.

Both ICT Specialist / GIS Specialist are highly skilled professionals who play an important role in the field of information technology and may use their skills to solve complex problems. An ICT Specialist may work in a variety of industries, including healthcare, finance, and education, and have broad range of skills in computer hardware and software. A GIS Specialist might also work in very different sectors but has specialized knowledge and skills in geographic information systems (GIS).

Concrete examples of professional profiles are software developers that develop the software that is used to share and integrate location data, working with a variety of programming languages and technologies. They can also be system administrators that maintain and manage the computer systems and networks that are used to share and integrate location data. They can also be GIS professionals using GIS software to solve a variety of problems, such as land use planning, environmental monitoring, and disaster response.

The following list provides examples of the specific knowledge, skills, and competencies that an ICT Specialist or GIS Specialist might need to possess when dealing with location data interoperability tasks:

- Proficiency in different computer systems and languages
- Knowledge of location data sharing standards
- Knowledge of location data formats and geospatial databases
- Knowledge on location data security and privacy
- Experience with location data integration, conversion, and transformation tools
- Experience with location data visualization tools
- Experience with location data analysis tools.

This profile should be also able to analyse user needs, as well as functional and interface requirements, and based on this, define, and design applications needed by the end user.

Ideally this profile will be also able to implement the most suitable methodologies and procedures for programming and implementation of geospatial applications for different types of platforms (desktop, web, mobile), using different programming paradigms and environments.

The specific topics covered in advanced/technical training on location data interoperability will vary depending on the needs of the audience. However, the above list of knowledge, skills, and competencies provides a starting point for developing a training program. Attempting to cover all technical aspects linked to location data interoperability in a training program is impractical due to the extensive list of topics. Instead, by defining and developing business case studies, we can focus on more specific technical training needs.

4. Gaps and mismatches between the current educational offer and business needs in the field of location data interoperability.

In this chapter we investigate the gaps and mismatches between the current offer of education and especially training on location data interoperability (analysed in the DIS4SME report D2.1), and the needs of businesses and other stakeholders identified through the online survey and interviews conducted.

4.1. Key concepts

In the literature and policy debates on gaps and differences between supply of and demand for skills, many similar and related terms are used, often interchangeable and without clear definition or explanation, which leads to confusion over the different terms used. To begin this section, a clarification is provided of some key terms used in the debate on skills needs.

- **Skill mismatch** is the encompassing term which refers to various types of imbalances between the supply of skills and demand for skills. Imbalance means that there are situations where the supply of skills is less than the demand, but also the opposite – less demand than supply – is possible. Particular concepts are used for each of these situations. When talking about the imbalance between supply and demand, skills mismatch is the preferred term. Also in this report, skills mismatch is used as the central term.
- The concepts of skills shortages and skills gaps are used to refer to the situation where the supply of skills is less than the demand for skills. **Skills shortage** refers to the situation when supply is less than demand on the skilled job market. Key indicator for skills shortages are vacancies for skilled workers that are hard to fill. The term **skills gap** on the other hand, is mainly used for the situation where demand exceeds supply internally within a firm or organization.
- It should be noticed that also a situation might arise or exist where the supply of skills is greater than demand in the market for skills. As a result, skilled workers might not be able to find an appropriate job or could be in work but not fully utilize their skills and education in

their current workplace. In other words, they could be **over-skilled or over-educated**. Also in this way, there might be a mismatch between supply and demand for skills.

- Finally, also a situation where a balance exists between skills supplied and skills demand, can be sub-optimal. This is expressed by the term '**skills deficit**', which refers to a job market in equilibrium with supply equalling demand, yet both supply and demand are below what they could be. In this 'low-skills equilibrium', employers have too low ambitions or are too risk averse in their search for skills, while at the same time the skills of workers and job searchers remain too low.

It is important to notice that the evidence collected as part of the DIS4SME survey and interviews especially deals with **skills needs and the mismatch** between these needed skills and the skills currently addressed and developed in existing education and training. For this reason, we prefer to use these two terms.

4.2. Current state of supply of vocational training on location data interoperability

In addition to the assessment of the needs for skills and training on location data interoperability and related topics, the DIS4SME project also investigated the existing offer of training on location data interoperability. The results of the DIS4SME study on 'Trends and challenges on location data interoperability education and training' are presented and discussed in a separate deliverable (Deliverable 2.1). In this section, we briefly summarize the methodology and main results and findings of this study, which allows us to afterwards investigate and determine the mismatches between the offer of training on one hand and the demand for training and skills on the other hand.

The focus of the analysis of the current supply of training was on training (courses) dealing with or related to data interoperability, and location data interoperability in particular. The specific objectives of the study were as follows:

- To provide an overview of the current landscape of training on location data interoperability and related topics
- To identify the core topics and skills addressed in the existing training on (location) data interoperability.

- To collect relevant training resources, materials and good practices that could be used for the design, development and delivery of training on location data interoperability in the context of DIS4SME.

Relying on a combination of manual and (semi-)automated approaches for discovering relevant materials, 98 training resources on (location) data interoperability were identified and further investigated. These resources included a variety of training options such as programs, courses, modules, seminars, and webinars.

In general, the training resources that were identified and investigated consisted of two main categories of training: while there were several courses dealing with GI, GIS and especially SDIs (and topics related to these), there's also was big group of courses focusing on (open) data and (digital) technology in general.

A key result of the study was the identification of **20 core concepts** in the existing offer of training. For each of these concepts, we identified the main courses in which the topic is covered, the learning objectives associated to the concept and a set of related topics that often are addressed in the same set of courses. In table 1 we present the 20 core concepts, with information on the courses in which these concepts are addressed.

Concepts	Related courses
Metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improving open data and metadata quality. • Procedures for Data and Metadata Harmonization. • Metadata and Catalogue Services.
Spatial Data Infrastructures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to SDI Architecture and Components • Spatial Representations and Spatial Data Infrastructures: Geoportals as SDI Interfaces • Spatial Representations and Spatial Data Infrastructures: Spatial Referencing as an SDI Foundation
AI & machine learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Artificial Intelligence for geodata • Monitoring and understanding emerging geospatial technologies • Understand and Manage the Digital Transformation in the Workplace

Semantic web and linked data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to a Web of Linked Data MOOC • Semantic Web Technologies' • Introduction to Linked Data and the Semantic Web
Web services and network services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spatial Representations and Spatial Data Infrastructures: Web Map vs Web Feature Services' • Introduction Open GIS Web Services • INSPIRE Network Services
Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Management • Service Management
Harmonization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Harmonisation • Procedures for Data and Metadata Harmonization • Semantic and Organisational Interoperability
Interoperability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interoperability: An introductory course • ArcGIS Data Interoperability in Action' • Spatial Representations and Spatial Data Infrastructures: Standards for Interoperability'
API	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Common Aspects of the OGC API Standards • Other OGC API Standards • Applications for OGC APIs
Government and policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measuring the impact of open data' • Open and Smart Government MOOC' • Introducing open data: What is open data
Knowledge graphs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge Graphs - Foundations and Applications • Knowledge Graphs
Open data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open data from theory to practice: data that creates value • Open Data and Licences • Measuring the impact of open data

Legal / legislation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introducing open data' • Understanding the legal side of open data' • INSPIRE Data and service sharing
Sharing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Literacy – What is it and why does it matter?' • Innovative Public Services: Knowledge Exchange • Introducing open data: What is open data?'
Visualization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Including data in your communication • Introducing data visualization • Geo-Spatial and web technologies
(Data) quality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open data from theory to practice: quality and validation • Quality aspects of geodata • Data Quality
(Data) models	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Semantic Modelling • Open data from theory to practice: modelling and enrichment • Spatial Representations and Spatial Data Infrastructures: Basic Representations of Spatial Entities
Data spaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data and Service Integration • Moving towards data spaces • Understanding data governance with open data
Digital transformation & digital technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Impact from Digital Transformation • The Digital Revolution • Understand and Manage the Digital Transformation in the Workplace
Public services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU Interoperability Academy: Innovative Public Services • European Interoperability Framework (EIF) Online Training

Table 1: Core concepts in the existing offer of training

In a second stage of the analysis, we aimed to identify clusters of related concepts and related courses. Seven main clusters of course topics were identified:

- **Spatial Data Infrastructures**, including concepts (or covering topics) such as network services, spatial (data) infrastructures, web services, geospatial quality, implementing rule(s), catalogue service, metadata standards and other.
- **Legal/Governance**, including concepts (or covering topics) such as: open data licences, international law, basic interoperability, selecting right licence, software licences among others.
- **Interoperability**, including concepts (or covering topics) such as: European interoperability framework, business process, e-government development, share information, interoperability reference and other.
- **Standards**, including concepts (or covering topics) such as: API standard, event stream, share geospatial data, geospatial web, web service, interoperability standard, access standard feature among others.
- **Data sharing and access**, including concepts (or covering topics) such as: 'service share, implement rule, spatial infrastructure, geospatial service, infrastructure defaces share, facilitate access, rule conformity',
- **Digital transformation**, including concepts (or covering topics) such as public services, public service innovation, digital transformation, artificial intelligence, impact measurement, new and emerging technologies, digital revolution, and other.
- **Knowledge representation**, including concepts (or covering topics) such as: knowledge graph, semantic web, semantic element, representation knowledge, knowledge production, semantic query among others.

In combination with the DIS4SME analysis on the current demand for training on location data interoperability, and the assessment of the skills gaps and mismatches between the offer of training and the demand for skills, this study will serve as important input to the definition of the DIS4SME curriculum, the co-creation of training materials and the delivery of DIS4SME training courses, which will cover skills and knowledge areas that are insufficiently addressed in the existing offer.

4.3 Analysis of the skills mismatch

The previous section focused on the supply side of skills and training on location data interoperability, which covers just one side of the assessment of skills gaps and mismatches. It is in combination with the identification and assessment of the demand for skills on location data interoperability, which is presented in chapter 2 of this report, that we can explore the mismatches between the offer of training on one hand and the demand for training and skills on the other hand.

The results and findings of the survey and the interviews presented in this report, allow us to better understand the demand for skills on location data interoperability. Several important skills needs areas, on which a strong need for skills was expressed by various stakeholders, could be identified:

- Data harmonization and semantic interoperability.
- Technical interoperability between different systems/tools/platforms.
- Advanced topics such as AI, IoT, big data, machine learning, APIs, etc.
- Legal issues related to data access, sharing and use.
- Practical aspects of data interoperability on real cases.

When comparing these skills needs with the topics covered and skills addressed in the existing offer of training, we see that already some training is provided on most of these aspects. This is illustrated in table 2, which shows examples of courses covering these five areas of skills needs.

Skills needs area	Related courses
Data harmonization and semantic interoperability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Semantic and Organisational Interoperability • Principles for Data and Metadata Harmonisation according to INSPIRE • Data Harmonisation • Procedures for Data and Metadata Harmonization • Semantic Modelling
Technical interoperability between different systems/tools/platforms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spatial Representations and Spatial Data Infrastructures: Standards for Interoperability • Interoperability: An introductory course • Introduction Open GIS Web Services

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to SDI Architecture and Components • INSPIRE Network Services
Advanced topics such as AI, IoT, big data, machine learning, APIs, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitoring and understanding emerging geospatial technologies • Artificial Intelligence for geodata • Common Aspects of the OGC API Standards • Applications for OGC APIs • Knowledge Graphs - Foundations and Applications
Legal issues related to data access, sharing and use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introducing open data • Understanding the legal side of open data • INSPIRE Data and service sharing • Data Literacy – What is it and why does it matter? • Spatial Representations and Spatial Data Infrastructures: Open (Government) Data
Practical aspects of data interoperability on real cases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Joining Spatial and Statistical Data • Meteorological data integration • Digitalisation of Construction SMEs

Table 2: Skills needs areas and related courses.

Table 2 shows that several courses on each of these skills areas already exists. This means effective learning outcomes, training activities and learning materials exists on each of these areas, which could inspire and support the development of new training courses and training activities in the context of DIS4SME. What is least developed so far, is training on the practical aspects of data interoperability on cases in different domains.

Taking this into consideration, the DIS4SME curriculum and training offer could provide an added value to the existing offer of training in multiple ways:

- Covering all relevant aspects in a logical and coherent manner, by integrating them into an overarching curriculum on location data interoperability.

- Having a strong focus on businesses and SMEs in particular, and their needs with regard to location data interoperability, which is different from public sector focus in most existing trainings.
- Focusing on real cases and real problems these SMEs are dealing with and addressing all interoperability challenges related to a specific case in an integrated manner.
- Covering all relevant types of data, i.e. geospatial and non-geospatial, but recognising the added value of geospatial data.
- Building further on the existing offer of training on various aspects of location data interoperability but complementing this with new training activities and materials.

5. Conclusions

This deliverable provides a detailed overview of the work carried out in DIS4SME Task 2.2. The report thoroughly explores the challenges associated with location data interoperability, taking into account valuable feedback from over 120 individuals. By analysing the insights provided by this diverse group, we gain a comprehensive understanding of the obstacles faced in achieving seamless integration and exchange of location data.

Primary focus of the task has been on collecting data, followed by a detailed analysis of the gathered information. The deliverable reports on the findings of an online survey ¹¹ and a series of interviews to individuals, focused on location data interoperability.

The responses offer a representative overview of the situation in each partner country as well as in other European countries. Most of the respondents were connected to SMEs and the most frequently mentioned problems were related to data format compatibility, interoperability between tools and platforms, data access and sharing problems due to legal or licensing restrictions, and converting geospatial data provided with different coordinate systems.

The collected data provides valuable insights into the areas where training is most needed, allowing us to prioritize our efforts accordingly. Based on the analysis of the responses collected from the online survey and the conducted interviews, several recommendations in the context of training in location data interoperability can be drafted. These recommendations are important in view of the definition of the DIS4SME training offer to be carried out in the next phases of the project.

There is a growing need for education and training on location data interoperability. To address this need, some recommendations include:

- There is a general need for more awareness and knowledge on the advantages of **standardization** when storing and sharing location data. This would make it easier to integrate location data from different sources. Knowledge of the standards is present but needs to be enhanced. Training should provide an overview of current standards, their use, and benefits.
- While knowledge of GIS tools seems to be relatively good, training (and practical examples) in **data conversion and transformation tools**, especially for performing schema mapping,

¹¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/DIS4SME>

data harmonization, and other operations that support semantic interoperability, appears to be lacking.

- There is a need for more **open-source software** to be used in the context of location data interoperability. This would make it more accessible and affordable for organizations to implement location data interoperability tasks. Training in location data interoperability should provide knowledge and skills primarily on OS software more than commercial applications.
- **Practical training** in the implementation of location data interoperability in different sectors and industries is crucial. Access to practical examples and training based on real cases can have a much greater impact and be of great help to SMEs. Our analysis concludes that there is currently a lack of training on the practical aspects of location data interoperability across different domains, which requires further attention.
- There is a need to raise more awareness regarding **policies and access to open data**. This will help individuals and organizations understand the importance of open data and how it can be utilized for various purposes. Additionally, it will encourage the creation of more open data resources and promote transparency and collaboration in data sharing.
- There are several **training formats** that can be effective for training SMEs in location data interoperability. Best options include short-term online training courses, hands-on workshops and webinars focused on specific topics or tools.

This report has also identified several key trends in the field of location data interoperability. These trends include:

- **IoT** is generating a vast amount of new location data. This is driving the need for new and innovative location data interoperability solutions.
- **AI** and machine learning is being used to develop new location data interoperability solutions that can automate tasks such as data cleaning and integration.
- **APIs and tools:** Professionals working with location data require practical courses on the use of specific tools. These courses should cover the relevance of essential tools such as Python programming, RESTful APIs, conversion and transformation tools like FME and HALE, data visualization and analysis tools like Kibana and Tableau, and geospatial data tools such as GeoPandas and GeoServer. These tools are currently crucial for tasks related to location data management, analysis, visualization, and integration.

This report also discusses the professional profiles that should be targeted by the training material to be developed in DIS4SME, based on information obtained from interviews and online surveys, as well as the knowledge and experience of educational experts. The identified profiles are Owner/manager/CEO/CTO of an SME and ICT Specialist/GIS Specialist.

While the training offer for managers and decision makers should cover the basics of location data interoperability and related policies, the training materials aimed at technical profiles include advanced and practical training providing the necessary knowledge and skills to implement data integration tasks. The text emphasizes the diverse and evolving needs of professionals in the field of location data interoperability and the importance of tailored training programs to bridge the gaps and meet these needs effectively.

Section 4 of this report investigates the gaps and mismatches between the current supply of education and training on location data interoperability and the needs of the market identified in section 2. It provides an overview of the current state of vocational training on location data interoperability as collected in deliverable 2.1 and maps identified training resources with the identified skills needs, enabling us to evaluate the extent to which these resources meet the identified needs.

Based on the feedback received from the online survey and interviews, several areas where there is a strong need for skills, as expressed by various stakeholders, were identified. These areas are the following:

- Data harmonization and semantic interoperability.
- Technical interoperability between different systems/tools/platforms.
- Advanced topics such as AI, IoT, APIs, etc.
- Legal issues related to data access, sharing and use.
- Practical aspects of data interoperability on real cases.

Although the existing training offer covers some of these areas, further development of training materials is needed to address all the identified skills needs. Additional analysis is needed to determine the extent of modifications required and the possibilities of reuse exiting materials. In the best-case scenario, some adaptation may be necessary to ensure that the materials are suitable for our specific needs. While these existing materials offer a strong basis for creating our courses, we

may still need to develop additional courses from scratch to fulfil the requirements of the training curricula.

It is noteworthy that the development of the business case studies in the next phases of the project will be key in order to address the lack of training in practical examples of location data interoperability. This will also likely require developing new materials from scratch.

To sum up, we hope that the work conducted in Task 2.2 will serve as a valuable source of inspiration and support for the development of the DIS4SME curriculum, as well as for the creation of new training courses and activities.

Annexes

Annex I: Online survey results

This section compiles graphically the summary of responses from participants who completed the survey.

1.1 What type of organisation are you working for?

		Answers	Ratio
Small and medium-size enterprise		51	48.57 %
Large enterprise		8	7.62 %
Public body		21	20 %
Training provider (including higher education)		7	6.67 %
Not for profit organisation		12	11.43 %
Freelance		2	1.9 %
Startup		3	2.86 %
Other (please specify)		7	6.67 %
No Answer		0	0 %

1.2 In which European country is your organisation located?

	Answers	Ratio
International organisation	1	0.95 %
European organisation	2	1.9 %
Austria	0	0 %
Belgium	5	4.76 %
Bulgaria	1	0.95 %
Croatia	13	12.38 %
Republic of Cyprus	0	0 %
Czech Republic	0	0 %
Denmark	0	0 %
Estonia	0	0 %
Finland	0	0 %
France	2	1.9 %
Germany	7	6.67 %
Greece	0	0 %
Hungary	1	0.95 %
Ireland	0	0 %
Italy	28	26.67 %
Latvia	0	0 %
Lithuania	0	0 %
Luxembourg	0	0 %
Malta	1	0.95 %
Netherlands	1	0.95 %
Poland	1	0.95 %
Portugal	1	0.95 %
Romania	0	0 %
Slovakia	0	0 %
Slovenia	10	9.52 %
Spain	27	25.71 %
Sweden	1	0.95 %
Other non EU country	3	2.86 %
No Answer	0	0 %

1.3 Please indicate the sector or sectors in which your organisation mainly operates.

		Answers	Ratio
Agriculture		18	17.14 %
Industry		21	20 %
Energy		18	17.14 %
Mobility		11	10.48 %
Transportation and logistics		18	17.14 %
Retail and marketing		2	1.9 %
Tourism and hospitality		7	6.67 %
Cultural heritage		4	3.81 %
Training and education		25	23.81 %
Software development/distribution		54	51.43 %
Architecture, engineering and construction		16	15.24 %
Urban planning		12	11.43 %
Environment		22	20.95 %
Finance		2	1.9 %
Real estate		7	6.67 %
Insurance		1	0.95 %
Utilities		12	11.43 %
Health		7	6.67 %
Media		2	1.9 %
Other (please specify)		17	16.19 %
No Answer		0	0 %

1.4 What is your role in the organisation?

		Answers	Ratio
Owner / Chief Executive Officer		24	22.86 %
Chief Technology Officer / Chief Information Officer		18	17.14 %
Human Resource Manager		0	0 %
Innovation Manager		3	2.86 %
Project Manager		31	29.52 %
Trainer / Professor / Researcher		21	20 %
Other (please specify)		19	18.1 %
No Answer		0	0 %

2.1 Are you familiar with the concept of location data interoperability?

		Answers	Ratio
Yes, very familiar		42	40 %
Yes, somewhat familiar		48	45.71 %
No, not familiar at all		13	12.38 %
Not sure/Don't know		2	1.9 %
No Answer		0	0 %

2.2 How would you rate your own level of expertise in relation to using and integrating location data?

		Answers	Ratio
Basic		27	25.71 %
Intermediate		38	36.19 %
Expert		34	32.38 %
No opinion		6	5.71 %
No Answer		0	0 %

2.3 Have you ever experienced issues in one or more of the following location interoperability aspects?

		Answers	Ratio
Data format compatibility Problems integrating geospatial data formats (such as Shapefile, GeoJSON, KML, TIFF, PostGIS, GML, Geopackage, etc.) with other geospatial or non-geospatial data stored in various formats (such as CSV, Excel, textual data, etc.)		74	70.48 %
Interoperability between tools and platforms Problems when using and exchanging location data across different tools, platforms, or software systems.		67	63.81 %
Coordinate systems conversion Problems when converting geospatial data provided with different coordinate systems.		58	55.24 %
Semantic interoperability Your geospatial data use different classification systems or vocabularies to represent the same features or attributes.		51	48.57 %
Data access and sharing Problems in accessing or sharing geospatial data due to legal or licensing restrictions and lack of sharing standards.		59	56.19 %
Schema mapping and data harmonization /transformation: Problems when mapping the attributes and fields between datasets and transforming the data to match the desired structure.		38	36.19 %
Legal interoperability: Problems when ensuring that legal frameworks related to privacy, data protection, intellectual property rights, and other relevant laws are compatible and harmonized to facilitate the exchange and use of location data.		32	30.48 %
Organisational interoperability: Problems when effectively sharing, exchanging and using location data generated and managed by multiple organisations, such as government agencies, private companies, research institutions, and non-profit organizations.		43	40.95 %
Other kind of problems (please specify)		2	1.9 %
No opinion		9	8.57 %
No Answer		0	0 %

2.4 Which of the following types of data do you work with and do you need to integrate with other (location and non-location) data?

		Answers	Ratio
Demographic information or population statistics		34	32.38 %
Business data (customer information, sales data or stock market data)		36	34.29 %
Temperature, humidity, air quality, or any other meteorological or environmental parameters		50	47.62 %
Economic indicators		20	19.05 %
Healthcare statistics		20	19.05 %
Social media data (social media feeds, check-ins, and user-generated content)		10	9.52 %
Cultural heritage		16	15.24 %
Image and raster data (satellite imagery, aerial photographs, or scanned maps)		64	60.95 %
Other (please specify)		24	22.86 %
No opinion		4	3.81 %
No Answer		0	0 %

2.5 How would you assess your knowledge regarding the use of tools and standards for sharing and integrating location data? : Web Service Standards: Such as the Web Map Service (WMS), Web Feature Service (WFS), and Web Coverage Service (WCS).

		Answers	Ratio
Basic		20	19.05 %
Intermediate		29	27.62 %
Expert		40	38.1 %
No knowledge		16	15.24 %
No Answer		0	0 %

2.5 How would you assess your knowledge regarding the use of tools and standards for sharing and integrating location data? : Geospatial Data Standards: Such as Geography Markup Language (GML), Keyhole Markup Language (KML), GeoJSON and GeoPackage.

		Answers	Ratio
Basic		20	19.05 %
Intermediate		33	31.43 %
Expert		34	32.38 %
No knowledge		18	17.14 %
No Answer		0	0 %

2.5 How would you assess your knowledge regarding the use of tools and standards for sharing and integrating location data? : Spatial Metadata Standards: Such as ISO 19115, FGDC CSDGM, GeoDCAT-AP and OGC Catalogue Service for the Web (CSW).

		Answers	Ratio
Basic		23	21.9 %
Intermediate		36	34.29 %
Expert		14	13.33 %
No knowledge		32	30.48 %
No Answer		0	0 %

2.5 How would you assess your knowledge regarding the use of tools and standards for sharing and integrating location data? : Spatial Processing and Analysis Standards: Such as Web Processing Service (WPS) or Styled Layer Descriptor (SLD).

		Answers	Ratio
Basic		39	37.14 %
Intermediate		21	20 %
Expert		12	11.43 %
No knowledge		33	31.43 %
No Answer		0	0 %

2.5 How would you assess your knowledge regarding the use of tools and standards for sharing and integrating location data? : Sensor Data Standards: Such as Sensor Observation Service (SOS) and SensorML.

		Answers	Ratio
Basic		35	33.33 %
Intermediate		19	18.1 %
Expert		10	9.52 %
No knowledge		41	39.05 %
No Answer		0	0 %

2.5 How would you assess your knowledge regarding the use of tools and standards for sharing and integrating location data? : 3D and City Model Standards: Such as CityGML or IndoorGML.

		Answers	Ratio
Basic		41	39.05 %
Intermediate		21	20 %
Expert		6	5.71 %
No knowledge		37	35.24 %
No Answer		0	0 %

2.5 How would you assess your knowledge regarding the use of tools and standards for sharing and integrating location data? : Semantic Web standards: W3C standards like Resource Description Framework (RDF), Web Ontology Language (OWL), and SPARQL.

		Answers	Ratio
Basic		33	31.43 %
Intermediate		23	21.9 %
Expert		7	6.67 %
No knowledge		42	40 %
No Answer		0	0 %

2.5 How would you assess your knowledge regarding the use of tools and standards for sharing and integrating location data? : GIS Software tools: Such as ArcGIS, QGIS, and other tools.

		Answers	Ratio
Basic		15	14.29 %
Intermediate		29	27.62 %
Expert		47	44.76 %
No knowledge		14	13.33 %
No Answer		0	0 %

2.5 How would you assess your knowledge regarding the use of tools and standards for sharing and integrating location data? : Integration Conversion and Transformation tools: Such as FME, ogr2ogr, GDAL and HALE.

		Answers	Ratio
Basic		21	20 %
Intermediate		33	31.43 %
Expert		16	15.24 %
No knowledge		35	33.33 %
No Answer		0	0 %

2.6 Which types of training resources would you consider most interesting to strengthen your knowledge in location data interoperability?

		Answers	Ratio
Distance learning (e-learning) short courses		75	71.43 %
In-house training short courses		27	25.71 %
Online workshops		56	53.33 %
Webinars		57	54.29 %
Short online videos		61	58.1 %
Slidesets and presentations		25	23.81 %
Downloadable technical guides		47	44.76 %
Hands on exercises and tutorials		50	47.62 %
Other (please specify)		1	0.95 %
No opinion		1	0.95 %
No Answer		0	0 %

Do you want to be informed about the follow up of this survey and about DIS4SME in general?

		Answers	Ratio
Yes, keep me informed (we will ask your contact information)		43	40.95 %
No thanks		62	59.05 %
No Answer		0	0 %

Annex II: Interviews summaries

Annex 2 compiles the information from each interview summarized by key parameters.

The names of the companies and experts have been omitted for data protection reasons.

Interviews in Spain

Interview 1.

Interviewee profile: Project manager

Company profile: Public company of the Regional Government

Date: 23/06/2023

Duration: 23:35

Place: Online

Interview highlights:

- The company works software development, tax services and geographic services.
- The software development system is its main source of monetary income.
- Manage location data for the fire and police system as well as the 112-emergency telephone number.
- The company collaborated with the company Telefonica for the development of mobile geolocation software.
- It launches projects on interoperability of related data through the IBM cloud pack for data platform.
- It is a producer of geographic data and It is the reference in cartography, telematic maps, maps of uses, habitability, flooding, geographic information systems.

- It will participate in a European project of digital twins of cities, in which a project of digital twin of Pamplona for mobility and environment will be made.
 - It does not present problems with location data but gives the example of all emergency systems (police, fire brigade, health) where stable and highly reliable systems are used. It is mentioned that there are more organisational problems, and it is presented that there is no collaboration between entities or companies with this data.
 - It mentions standards such as Inspire for geographic data interoperability and GayaX.
 - It has a project to create the Data Hub in his region which has different challenges, one of them is the cultural, it presents courses, presentations on the subject of data where there may be topics such as location data.
 - It is interested in the topic of location interoperability courses; they see that there is not much on offer and would like an online model.
-

Interview 2

Interviewee profile: CIO (Chief Information Officer).

Date: 03/07/2023

Duration: 50 minutes

Place: Face-to-face

Interview highlights:

- The company works for the most important companies in Navarra in terms of document management and digitization.
- It has a private archive, where, after digitizing documents, it stores them with a very closed consultation system in case of inspection, requirement. It is the largest archive in his region.
- It is currently focused on the interoperability of management systems as well as the security of said systems and connections.
- Despite having a data interoperability area, it doesn't do anything related to location interoperability.

- The CIO comments that it was valued (location interoperability) for the issue of locating documentation in storage.
 - - It is the company in its region with the greatest knowledge in interoperability of management systems, invoicing, materials management, consumables, etc.
 - The interviewee comments that if the project focuses on locating his region, there will be SMEs that will be left out.
 - The interviewee concludes by indicating that in his region the issue of interoperability is still far away, even more in SMEs.
-

Interview 3

Interviewee profile: CTO

Date: 24/07/2023

Duration: 20 minutes

Place: Online

Interview highlights:

- The company was initially oriented to the execution of cartographic production works, evolving to become a company with a high innovative and technological profile. Their technology seeks efficiency in management, by exploiting all types of data, based on innovative processes.
- They have a platform for data collection, data selection and data analysis.
- They collect information beyond Geographic Information Systems. GIS/GIS, Artificial Intelligence, IoT, Smart Cities, georeferenced videos, drones in a collaborative environment.
- They believe that Spanish SMEs are far from data location interoperability. The few that value it hires external services.
- They might be interested in participating in the project. Either through its platform or as experts for content creation

Interview 4

Interviewee profile: RDI manager.

Date: 18/07/2023

Duration:

Place: Online

Interview highlights: The most relevant findings are the following:

- The SME subsector is the provision of services on hydrometeorology and risk management such as Early Warning and Decision Support systems (support and communication in case of climate-related events)
 - The SME manages all kinds of location data from different providers (Sensors, weather radar data, infrastructure, vulnerability maps, 112 calls, traffic disruptions)
 - Each data provider has a different system and format for data provision and sharing. Best way to share data is via RESTful API's but not all providers have one.
 - Standards for data sharing are few and not used. The SME has to convert data from providers to their own standard every time.
-

Interview 5

Interviewee profile: Development of R&D projects manager

Date: 09/08/2023

Duration: 43:05 minutes

Place: Online

Interview highlights:

- This company is a geolocation data consultancy, working with this data to generate area studies for the agri-food sector, such as pest or disease studies, field studies for mechanization and digitization of field work, farms, Irrigation.
 - One of the main problems that this company has in its day to day, is the standardization of data. The neighbouring regions seek to participate in their projects with the data collected in their plots but do not follow the same standards which makes it difficult or sometimes impossible the task.
 - The tools used in this company for the manipulation of geolocation data are: Qgis, Idenageoportal and Agroasor.
 - This company participates in a collective project with different Spanish institutions called SIEX (The Farming Information System will pursue the interoperability between the different sources of information available in the agricultural, livestock and forestry sectors; SIEX will be a set of interconnected databases and administrative records with information on farms in Spain.
 - SIEX will be technically and systematically interoperable with the Agricultural Holdings Registers of the Autonomous Communities, the Digital Agricultural Holdings Notebooks, and other public registers).
 - This company has participated in online training in different portals, but now she is more interested in specific training tailored to particular needs.
-

Interviews in Italy

Interview 1

Company profile: Public Technical agency

Interviewee profile: Public officer in Data management Service

Date: 06/07/2023

Duration: 30 minutes

Place: Online

Interview highlights:

Interview main outcomes are the following:

- There is a generic lack of knowledge of standards and regulations on location data interoperability.
- Training on regulatory aspects of location data interoperability are of great interest, not only to public administrations, but also to the private sector.
- The technical and semantic layers of interoperability can be seen as priorities, but legal interoperability is also important.
- Training should follow European priorities, in particular those related to the European Green Deal (environmental sector).
- Training should be modular and cover different levels of knowledge, from the most basic to the most technical, including the political level of decision-makers.
- The MOOC, including webinars and a practical session, is a good training formula.

Interview 2

Interviewee profile: Project Manager and Technical Manager

Date:30/06/2023

Duration: 23:35

Place: Online

Interview highlights:

Interview main outcomes are the following:

- Interoperability is a hot topic for her company, especially its technical layer.
- One of priorities in her company in the context of data integration is to foster the reuse of Copernicus data by public administrations.
- One of her company major needs is to have machine-readable catalogues.

- To have well-trained personnel is crucial as well.
 - To update on the normative and technological trends (related to location interoperability) the technicians already employed.
 - To assure that new resources are aligned with the rest of the team, in terms of location interoperability.
 - The recommended training includes:
 - 2 information days
 - A project work
 - In-person training is preferable to both online and hybrid modes.
-

Interview 3

Interviewee profile: Professor at the Department of Computer Science

Date: 10/07/2023

Duration: 25 minutes

Place: Online

Interview highlights:

Interview main outcomes are the following:

- When it comes to location data, there is a general misalignment between Academia, the repository of advanced theoretical knowledge, and the public sector, which deals with its practical application.
- To overcome this mismatch and guarantee interoperability, training on standards is essential.
- The technical and semantic layers of interoperability can be seen as priorities.
- Online courses are a good option for students and business. Face-to-face training is a preferred option for the public sector.

- Interoperability is important in all sectors. One criterion for prioritisation could be the areas where human health is involved: Health, Emergencies and Security.
-

Interview 4

Interviewee profile: Project manager

Date: 03/07/2023

Duration: 20 minutes

Place: Online

Interview highlights:

- There is a generic lack of knowledge of standards on location data interoperability, especially from public administrations.
 - The technical and semantic layers of interoperability can be seen as priorities.
 - It is important to raise awareness on interoperability standards in order to meet the future challenges.
 - In the case of datasets that use other data as a geographical reference, it is important that all public administrations use the same references to avoid inconsistencies.
 - The preferred training method is either face-to-face or hybrid (i.e., a face-to-face meeting followed by a series of asynchronous online appointments).
 - The area of dynamic sensor data is a priority in terms of location data interoperability.
-

Interview 5

Interviewee profile: CEO

Date: 11/07/2023

Duration: 25 minutes

Place: Online

Interview highlights:

Regarding relevancy of external agents, mostly software providers were mentioned as well as universities that can give data integration – and new knowledge and they can push the open data for the data integration.

The skill set needed, in connection with what was mentioned before, would be initially found in universities, prominently in software engineers. People fresh out of universities might be better equipped from a technical/background point of view, while older generations can improve their skill set via learning of the field, since in IT staying up to date with new languages and framework is crucial. This is not always easy to achieve since, due to busy hours, finding time for both internal and external training is not always easy, since it means stealing time from the “working” hours.

One aspect that emerged is that, given the specificity of competences needed in such a small company, it is more common that the training needed is from pre-existing personnel, rather than looking for external courses. In addition to that, on-line many free specific resources can be found to support technical growth (YouTube, LinkedIn); the issue is that these sources are not legitimized or homogenous, and most of them are in English.

Large language model is, and will be, relevant for improving and supporting interoperability formation.

Interview 6

Interviewee profile: Professor at University and co-founder.

Date:19/07/2023

Duration:23 minutes

Place: Online

Interview highlights:

- His company is a spin-off of the University, where professors and researchers are operating to industrialize and bring to market research activities. The aim of his company is to develop and provide tools and technologies to synchronize data, sharing documents and synchronizing copies through a specific IT platform.

- In particular the synchronization of spreadsheets is addressed, being Excel tools the most diffused tool which people around the world use to manage numerical data; security is ensured by using KPIs, in which data are encrypted at the source and decrypted at the destination.
- Spreadsheets can contain very different kinds of data (numbers, streets, tables, charts, pictures), each characterized by a specific mechanism of presentation; in the connection among different spreadsheets, it is assumed that all data are coded according to Excel standard.
- A major problem is that to share some specific data is normally necessary to share the whole spreadsheet located in the Google services, so, at least in general, out of the EU; this aspect is considered critical by the Commission, but also by many enterprises. Synthetically: synchronizing data on its own IT system is safer than sharing spreadsheets in the cloud.
- Presently his company does not explicitly deal with located data, as location data is one of the possible data that it tools are synchronizing: interoperability is therefore considered as hidden inside Excel spreadsheets. So far his company has not had the opportunity to synchronize location data, but this one is an important expected evolution of its product, for example in the context of Internet of Things applications (typically in IoT data are moving and changing their location).
- Learning something more on location data is considered by his company as an opportunity to lead a best service, but so far they did not specifically investigate on training tools available on the market; by sure the services expected to be provided by DIS4SME should be of interest for him, in particular short courses for technical people designing and developing software.
- To promote the participation of him in DIS4SME training initiative, the project will provide to him, as soon as available, final conclusions of interviews and surveys summarizing all the contributions by the external experts.

Interview 7

Interviewee profile: CEO, PhD in Engineering

Date:27/07/2023

Duration: 10 minutes

Place: Online

Interview highlights:

- Technical experts from need tools for data sharing to make analysis faster.
- The main difficulties appointed from training are related to the need to have standards for different tools.
- As far as concerns external agents, they have some partners because when they don't have specific tools or Hardware, they can ask them. They use external tools for some consultancy, for example they collaborate with CNR (National Research Organisation) and University. In their interoperability his company manage and share data with different partners.
- Their team is composed by engineers, informatics, or computer scientists, so the main training and talent needs are linked to scientific issues.
- In general, it could be interesting and very helpful to have some webinar, tutorial or documentation on how to create standards or how to manipulate data for best sharing.

Interview 8

Interviewee profile: Founding partner and CEO.

Date of the interview: 31.07.2023

Duration: 30 minutes

Place: Online

Interview highlights:

Interview main outcomes are the following:

- The interview provides a viewpoint of a wider community represented by the many trainees following the TerreLogiche training courses on GI.
- The weak ring of the interoperability exploitation chain is undoubtedly represented by the Public Administrations, as procurers of GI based services and, as such, possible

interoperability enablers. They lack of “cultural interoperability” (basic interoperability principles), that should be added as a fifth layer to the EIF interoperability stack.

- The most relevant knowledge and skill gaps are related to GI basic knowledge and skills, the use of the tools, the search and use of satellite data, primarily Copernicus data.
 - Despite there are no data that can be classified as non-geospatial, a couple of sectors where a major integration of geospatial data would be beneficial are epidemiology and geomarketing.
 - The most effective way to deliver the courses is synchronously, by remote, not exceeding 18-20 hours organised in sessions of max 2 half days per week.
 - Vertical sectors which can be considered as priorities for interoperability aspects are environmental monitoring (especially by means of sensors), territorial planning, renewable energies.
-

Interview 9

Interviewee profile: project manager

Date of the interview: 24/07/2023

Duration: -

Place / Method: Email

Interview highlights: The most relevant findings are the following:

- The company works in different sectors and examples of location data are real time position of vehicles and client or customers addresses.
- Integration problems are mainly integration geospatial data in data visualisation, business intelligence and exploration tools such as Kibana and Tableau
- They use GeoPandas <https://geopandas.org/en/stable/about.html> to solve location data interoperability problems.

Interview 10**Interviewee profile:** CEO**Date of the interview:** 18/09/21023**Duration:** 20 min**Place / Method:** online**Interview highlights:** The most relevant findings are the following:

- Mission of the SME is to transform agriculture and promote sustainability through the power of artificial intelligence (AI) and location data.
- SME offerings revolve around harnessing AI-driven insights from a rich tapestry of location data sources. They provide a suite of products and services that empower farmers, land managers, and agricultural stakeholders to make informed decisions.
- SME faces common interoperability obstacles encountered when integrating location data with diverse sources and systems. These challenges include disparate data structures, communication protocol disparities, and spatial resolution disparities. To overcome these hurdles, adopts a set of best practices:
 - Standardized Data Structures
 - Meticulous pre-processing procedures to clean and prepare data for analysis,
 - Storage Solutions

Training and Future Directions: they are open to short courses focusing on data visualization, with an emphasis on spatially distributed information. They aim to enhance their expertise in utilizing specific tools and platforms for data visualization and transformation, further solidifying their position as leaders in sustainable agriculture powered by AI and location data.

Interview in Sweden

Interview 1

Interviewee profile:

University Professor / consultant

Date: 07/08/2023

Duration: -

Place: Email

Interview highlights:

The most relevant findings are the following:

- Data harmonisation and schema transformation problems are solved using HALE software, for instance on the Harmonisation to INSPIRE data models.
- It seems that the data integration business is going in the JSON direction. It seems that many data integration service companies are providing solutions based on JSON as the main data exchange mechanism.

Interviews in Croatia

Interview 1

Interviewee profile: Holds MS degree in Geodesy and Geoinformatics.

Date: 03.07.2023.

Duration: 60 minutes

Place: Online

Interview highlights:

Multiple domain experts from ISRBC member countries (Slovenia, Croatia, Serbia, Bosnia and Herzegovina) must use various location data-oriented tools (both custom developed and COTS) and often have problems with those, caused by the lack of awareness of the basic geospatial data concepts. Those people would benefit from introductory trainings on geospatial data but with focus on the actual skills needed for their work (basic geospatial data management and updating). High level training (semantic consistency, new trends in EU level data management directions) would be interesting for those with strong technical and geospatial data background.

Interview 2

Interviewee profile: Technical project manages

Date: 07.07.2023.

Duration: 50 minutes

Place: Online

Interview highlights:

The subject company is focused on the data with an emphasis on, but not limited to, its location component and the technologies for managing it. In situations where the data is of a syntactically low quality level, a certain amount of work is now days needed to improve it, it is still manageable. On the other hand, when semantical problems exist with the data it is sometimes almost impossible to make it really useful.

Interview 3

Interviewee profile: GIS and spatial data infrastructure consultant

Date: 14.07.2023.

Duration: 35 minutes

Place: Online

Interview highlights:

- The data should be harmonized according to the INSPIRE specifications and their availability should be enabled through the services in accordance with the technical specifications. When working with data, there is a reconciliation of data because it can happen that the maps have different originals. The data needs to be adapted to the database used to create the map. The main problem is not even different sources, but the unstructured nature of the data (there are many CADs), data are not properly numbered at the local or national level and comes without documentation.
- Appropriate tools, standards, and practices: There are no standards because each data or part of data is adjusted separately. Although they have software tools with which analyses are made, it is often a problem to detect what is needed from the input data. But in the company, they do not perceive this as a problem, this is the situation with data. There is also a lot of manual work, because very often the topology is not correct, the data are not in the same layers, but they consider it an integral part of the job.
- The problem for new employees is recognizing the unstructured nature of the data. There is no awareness of this when they are first employed. It's one thing to read about it in a book, and another when you get a large amount of data and you have to open and look at each one. Employees know the operations, but they don't recognize the problem until they start working on it. And this is the segment where we guide them through the process.
- The employees have acquired knowledge and understanding through practical work examples. Their learning process involved gaining experience and insights from real-life situations encountered during their work.
- He believes that his experience from SGA and from a private company definitely helped him in recognizing the need for standardization and interoperability of data. He has not encountered many applications that aggregate data from different systems. It would hardly be possible to make a unique course.
- The employees have acquired knowledge and understanding through practical work examples. Their learning process involved gaining experience and insights from real-life situations encountered during their work.
- He believes that his experience from SGA and from a private company definitely helped him in recognizing the need for standardization and interoperability of data. He has not encountered many applications that aggregate data from different systems. It would hardly be possible to make a unique course.

Interview 4

Interviewee profile: director of GIS operations.

Date of the interview: 16.07.2023.

Duration: 45 minutes

Place: In person

Interview highlights:

As a part of a company deeply involved in geospatial data sector and a part of its management, he would (is a must at his position) consider participating in trainings aiming at current technological and other geospatial domain related advances. Not particularly interested in basic upskilling. Sees opportunities in upskilling the general population in basic geospatial concepts/skills.

Interviews in Belgium

Interview 1

Interviewee profile: CEO

Date: 31/07/2023

Duration: -

Place: Email

Interview highlights:

The most relevant findings are the following:

- He is currently working to set up a platform to exchange IACS data with farmers and partners. He can work with us in a potential BC on IACS data sharing and integration.

- FME software is a key tool on data integration processes in the IACS context and seems it is also a key in many other data integration processes involving geospatial data and other data sources. Therefore, training in DIS4SME should take this into account.
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Interview 2

Interviewee profile: Senior project manager

Date:27/07/2023

Duration: -

Place: Email

Interview highlights:

The most relevant findings are the following:

- His company deals mainly with location data (satellite, airborne, in situ data from sensors or field work)
- Main interoperability problems are on coordinate and projection systems for data from different sources, missing metadata, export data to desired formats and very important semantic a terminology issues.
- Use of FME to solve most interoperability problems and data conversions.
- Use of standards such as CityGML for 3D-city models to overcome interoperability problems.
- Suggestion of a Business Case based on Urban Tree Planting and the use of FME for data conversion.
- Training and in-house upskilling coming from the company's commercial software providers.